

An Augmented Guitar with Active Acoustics

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ABSTRACT

The present article describes and discusses an acoustic guitar augmented with structure-borne sound drivers attached on its soundboard. The sound drivers enable to drive electronic sounds into the guitar, transforming the soundboard into a loudspeaker and building a second layer of sonic activity on the instrument. The article presents the system implementation and its associated design process, as well as a set of sonic augmentations. The sound aesthetics of augmented acoustic instruments are discussed and compared to instruments comprising separate loudspeakers.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper presents an implementation of "active acoustics" on a steel-stringed acoustic guitar. The term "active acoustics" is employed here to signify a solid surface turned into a sound source with structure-borne sound drivers (or "vibration speakers"). In our case, an acoustic instrument's soundboard is excited with a sound driver, building a new layer of acoustic activity on the instrument.

The present work is part of the augmented instruments paradigm, where the sonic possibilities of an existing instrument are expanded via electronic means. However, the existing body of research on augmented instruments has made wide use of loudspeakers that are external to the initial instrument. Our approach investigates the possibility to conduct the sonic augmentation into the instrument itself, transforming the instrument into an electro-acoustic object (taken literally here) which radiates both the instrument's natural sound as well as the electronic sound. Our project thus stands at the crossroads of two research fields: augmented instruments and structure-borne sound. More specifically, the work explores the advantages provided by a hexaphonic pickup and two parallel vibration speakers in an active acoustic guitar design.

The methodological bias used in this project is one of artistic research. The design is driven by concrete musical needs stemming from an aesthetic preoccupation with the concept of "electro-acoustic chamber music". The work is part of a current trend towards a widening of the scope of electronic music beyond the loudspeaker paradigm and its associated social practices [1].

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2. BACKGROUND

A significant body of research has been achieved on augmented instruments, starting from the seminal work of Tod Machover's hyperinstruments project [2] and, even earlier, Gordon Mumma's hornpipe and related works [3]. More recently, the guitar has gained attention, with an ensemble of projects on electric guitar augmentation [4], the exploration on hexaphonic signal processing [5], as well as radical redesigns of the instrument [6]. The electric guitar itself can be seen as an augmentation stemming from the acoustic guitar via the electromagnetic microphone and analog (from the 80's onward, digital) signal processing [7].

In the domain of acoustic instruments, the area of "active control" of vibrating systems has gained significant attention [8][9]. Active control has been used successfully to modify the modal characteristics of string and wind instruments, with the aim of creating flexible, user controllable acoustics on physical instruments. Stemming from the work on active control, the IRCAM is currently developing an augmented acoustic instruments project under the title "SmartInstruments" [10] [11].

In the consumer electronics domain, a recent patent and a successful quickstarter project features a structure-borne sound driver for acoustic guitar, providing a set of basic audio effects driven into the guitar's back panel [12]. Named "Tonewood amp", the product targets a widespread market with traditional guitar effects. In contrast, our project aims for a radical sonic augmentation of the acoustic guitar, using hexaphonic signals and more adventurous digital signal processing techniques.

3. DESIGN PRINCIPLE

3.1 Design and implementation

The target of our design process is a fully user-controlled augmented acoustic guitar. The sonic possibilities of the instrument should be significantly expanded without hindering the instruments traditional playing techniques, and there should be no need for an external sound technician to operate the instrument. Moreover, after the initial trial period, the augmentation should be compacted to fit into the guitar or into its immediate periphery.

Our project is based on a Breedlove C20 professional-quality acoustic steel string guitar. The guitar is equipped with an Ubertar hexaphonic electromagnetic pickup [13]. Capturing the sound of each individual string is at the basis of our design. A monophonic pickup would provide a summed signal for all the polyphonic elements in the playing, leading to the impossibility to use, for example,

any detailed pitch-tracking, onset detection, or detailed spectral processing algorithms. Moreover, monophonic signal processing is easily stamped with the sonic imprint of the iconic "guitar effects", well developed since the analog era and heard on countless records and live shows. Our project aims to distance itself from the "guitar effects" and seek a drastic transformation of the guitar towards an electro-acoustic instrument, a tool for operating in the sonic domains of contemporary electronic music. The hexaphonic pickup enables to work on the spectral content of each string, as well as to perform detailed analysis on the playing which can be used as control input for signal processing. The hexaphonic output is pre-amplified and routed into Max/MSP via a RME Fireface audio interface. Audio processing takes place in a Max patch and the output is amplified and routed into two Hiwave 32C30-4B structure-borne audio drivers attached inside the guitar's soundboard. Figure 1 shows an outline of the system as well as the signal flow from the guitar strings back into the soundboard.

Figure 1. System schema and signal flow from the strings through the processing modules and into the soundboard.

The choice of two sound drivers stems from a perceptual work with the instrument and is not linked to the concept of stereo signal. The localization of a sound driver on a surface affects the sound color dramatically as different resonant modes are being excited. This phenomenon is emphasized by the irregular shape and the bracing of the guitar's soundboard. Starting out with just one sound driver, we were unable to find a single entirely satisfying location on the soundboard. Locations rich in low-end would have deep cuts in middle frequencies, producing a muddy sound. Locations with defined trebles showed a lack of low-frequency content. Thus via experimentation on the instrument, we found out that using two transducers enables to produce a smoother overall spectral response, as well as a more convincing sound diffusion from the instrument as one can feel the whole soundboard radiating. The driver placement was found via a perceptual trial and error. Figure 2. illustrates the placement of the sound drivers inside the guitar.

Figure 2. The position of the structure-borne sound drivers on the soundboard, inside the guitar.

3.2 Acoustic study of the system

Following this first exploratory phase we set out to measure the frequency response of each driver-plus-soundboard location couples on our specific guitar model. The HISS Tools Max/MSP library [14] sine sweep method was used in an acoustically controlled studio space. The goal was to provide measured data about the overall response and the prominent modal responses of each of the drivers, as well as of the whole system. The frequency responses are presented in figure 3.:

- 1) Driver 1 placed behind the bridge, shows a strong response around 100Hz, a huge cut at 250Hz and a series of peaks at approx. 450, 900, 1500 and 2500Hz.
- 2) Driver 2 placed near the fingerboard shows a weak low-end response, but a smoother overall profile. It may be used to compensate for the low-mid (150-300Hz) loss in driver 1. Prominent modes are found at 450, 1500, 2500 and 4000Hz.
- 3) The overall system response is shows a consistent mix of the individual driver's characteristics. Prominent modal resonance regions are found around 100Hz, between 450 and 1000Hz, as well as a gradual high-cut profile upwards from 1kHz.

The frequency response analysis of the system provides a basis for an informed equalization of the signals sent to the drivers. The system's frequency response may be compensated via digital filtering [15]. The main modal resonances of the overall system are identified. In the signals driven into the instrument they may be avoided for a clearer overall sound, or enhanced in order to provoke feedback.

1) Frequency response for sound driver 1

2) Frequency response for sound driver 2

3) Frequency response for both sound drivers combined

Figure 3. Frequency response representations for the sound driver - soundboard couples: 1) driver 1, 2) driver 2, 3) both drivers.

3.3 A modular design

For the moment our system is modular, composed of separate A/D conversion, (pre)amplification and processing stages, as well as a considerable amount of cables. The system's present state is not in line with our design goal of an integrated, compact instrument where the electronics would fuse with the instrument. However, at the present stage we are still in the process of constituting a proof of concept for the sonic relevancy of an acoustic augmented guitar. We are aiming towards a research-creation loop with a concert praxis with the present instrument. Real-life music-making experience will provide invaluable feedback for the design process. When this trial stage is completed, the possibility of miniaturization will be explored, in connection with the instrument's augmented part's interface design.

4. SOUND DESIGN AND AESTHETICS

Instrument augmentation seeks to enlarge the instrument's sonic possibilities while retaining its entire playability with the traditional techniques. In addition to this initial

agenda, our work is motivated by four personal considerations which are of aesthetic and artistic nature:

- Merge electronics and acoustics into one instrument
- The hybrid instrument should have an aural imprint similar to an acoustic instrument (spatial diffusion, spectral characteristics, volume)
- The electronics are not used for amplification, instead for augmentation of the instrument's sonic possibilities
- Avoid iconic guitar effects

A significant limitation of an acoustic augmented instrument is the inability to deduct the "original" acoustic sound from the instrument's sonic aggregate. The soundboard cannot be damped as the drivers' amplification depend on it, and in our current guitar the strings may not be decoupled from the soundboard. The augmented instrument presents itself as a "guitar plus electronics" system. It is thus impossible escape from the guitar-like sonic signature of the instrument and slide into a completely electronic soundscape. Of course, one may choose to not play and use the instrument as an object-loudspeaker for sound diffusion.

Our project's approach to sound design and aesthetics is based on an idea of sonic typology and complementarity. The acoustic guitar produces a range of sounds typical for a plucked string instrument. The sounds are harmonic (except on some specific playing techniques such as crossed strings or *golpe* hits), with a strong attack portion and a relatively short duration depending on the pitch and the acoustics of the instrument and strings, as there is no energy added to the vibration after the initial attack. By comparison with other traditional instruments and electronic sounds, it is straightforward to deduct a set of sound types the acoustic guitar is lacking. For example, one could think of sustained, percussive or inharmonic/noisy sounds. Also, any kind of modulation or modification of the sound after the attack is alien to the original guitar sound typology. In our perspective, one possible strategy for a fecund augmentation of an instrument is to identify sonic typologies which are absent from the instrument and work to expand it towards them. The aforementioned sound types have served as a guide in the sonic design process, producing four augmentations presented here: 1) long sounds; granular synthesis, 2) long sounds; modal feedback, 3) percussive sounds: attack timbre modification, and 4) Noisy sounds: cross-synthesis with flute fluttertongue sounds.

5. AUGMENTATIONS

A series of experimental augmentations for the active acoustic guitar have been implemented in Max&MSP. Video documentation of the augmentations can be found at http://otsola.org/?page_id=790.

Prior to these augmentation, all six microphone signals are individually equalized for better isolation from crosstalk and to de-emphasize frequency regions which correspond to the measured resonant modes (see figure 3.).

5.1 Hexaphonic granular synthesis

This augmentation uses a synthesized sound to prolong the natural sound of the plucked strings, creating an adjustable resonance to each note played. Each string is routed into a live sampling granular synthesis object (*msp munger~* external), and each string's input is monitored for attacks (with *msp bonk~* external). A detected attack actions a gain ramp, gradually bringing the synthesized granular sound into the mix in order to replace the waning natural sound. A "freeze" option runs the granular synthesizer in loop mode and offering the possibility to prolong the synthesized tones without limitations. The *munger~* object allows for a rich shaping of the granulation parameters, moreover with six channels running simultaneously.

5.2 Modal feedback

The modal feedback augmentation is a dynamic equalizer tuned to the main resonant modes of the guitar (100, 450, 1000Hz). These key frequencies are the "sensitive spots" of our guitar; any substantial energy driven into it at these frequencies will be trapped as a standing wave in the soundboard, amplified and easily transferred into the strings, thus forming a feedback loop with the microphone. Our augmentation uses a frequency-specific analyzer on the summed output of all the strings (*msp sigmund~* external) to monitor the energy on the key frequency bands. The analyzer output is mapped to the gain of three high-Q resonant filters (*msp cascade~*), augmenting the gains when the sound contains little energy at the key frequencies, and lowering the gains in case of overload. With careful tuning of the system, the augmentation produces a "hot" feedback on the guitar, just under control but giving a sense of the guitar responding to the playing with extreme sensitivity.

5.3 Attack timbre modification

Each string is monitored for attacks with the *msp bonk~* external. A detected attack triggers a percussive sample which is cross-synthesized with the original signal and driven into the soundboard. In our experiments, we used flute flutter-tongue attack samples and the *swinger~* cross synthesis external from the *fftease* library [16]. The system augments the percussive character of the guitar. It proves particularly effective with the palm-mute playing technique, producing hybrid "flute-guitar" attack sounds. We also experimented with further convolution processing of the hybrid timbres, adding an adjustable feeling of space in the sound. An interesting option is the application of a different impulse response convolution on each string, for example, larger halls for the lower strings and tighter spaces or objects for the upper strings. The guitar thus gains a sense of different spatial percepts - from large and reverberant to tiny and constricted - according to the string played.

5.4 Noisy signals

The guitar produces mainly harmonic sounds. In our sense, it would be musically engaging to be able to pro-

duce inharmonic timbres, and especially towards the noisier types of spectra. Our augmentation uses the same hexaphonic attack detection and sample playback system as the attack timbre modification patch described above. However, instead of short samples, long samples of flute air-noise are employed here, real-time cross-synthesized with the original signal. In addition, pitch detection (*msp sigmund~* external) on each string is used to dynamically drive a bank of 1-band resonant filters which constrict the noise spectrum to a narrow band around the note played. The result is an airy flute-like resonance added on the acoustic sound of the guitar.

6. DISCUSSION

While being at their very early and experimental stages, the augmentations presented in this paper provide engaging new sound possibilities for the acoustic guitar. Driving the processed sound into the guitar itself creates a coherent ensemble with the acoustic and the electronic sounds radiating from the same source. In this sense, the usual sonic dichotomy of the instrument - loudspeaker combination is bypassed in favor of a single instrumental entity. The aural image given by the electro-acoustic instrument is radically different from a loudspeaker: the guitar's directionality points towards a cardioid pattern over the whole spectrum, while loudspeakers radiate in a closed angle on high frequencies. Also, the audio spectrum modified by the guitar's tonewood results in a characteristic aural imprint for both acoustic and electronic sounds.

For the instrumentalist, the newfound simplicity of a single comprehensive sound tool can be an opportunity to focus and work in a tighter multimodal feedback loop with the instrument. One might argue in favor of a strong sense of embodiment with a single vibrating object between the hands and pressed against the torso, as opposed to a larger modular system with separate speakers, producing a sense of distance with the sound. With the sound radiating from the instrument itself, problems related to onstage monitoring are greatly reduced. Also, the sound level is that of an acoustic instrument - a desirable factor in the aesthetic perspective that motivates us, living with the aural fatigue of decades of (amplified music and urban soundscapes).

However, the present state of our system discards the question of the interface. The augmented part of the instrument is still running on a separate PC, interfaced with a mouse, keyboard and a screen. While our augmented instrument (re)gains its integrity in the domain of sound radiation, it still portrays a divide on the level of the interface. The current interface is an incoherent sum of a refined haptic instrument on one side, and a visual, symbolic computer interface on the other side. Thus the work towards a more integrated augmented instrument faces a major challenge. This ideal instrument would have not only the electronic and the acoustic sounds emanating from a single vibrating object, but would also present a coherent set of affordances tightly integrated on the instrument, and which would not counter the existing playing techniques.

On the technical level, the electromagnetic pickup used in this project would be favorably replaced by a hexaphonic piezoelectric one, producing less noise and being less prone to external disturbances such as stage lights. The level of crosstalk between strings/microphone channels would also be reduced, resulting in a higher precision in digital sound processing and analysis. Feedback is an issue when working with sounds close to the guitar's natural output, emphasizing its resonant frequencies and with high gain. We do not experience significant feedback problems on sounds which avoid reproducing the guitar's tone and its resonant frequencies, with sound intensity levels close to the initial acoustic sound. The possibility of feedback can also be used creatively, as in the modal feedback augmentation (see section 5.). Processing latency is a sensitive parameter for all live processing. In our augmentations, latency is especially apparent on more percussive sonic typologies such as the attack timbre morphing. Perceptually, with a typical ~20 millisecond latency the playing experience is still coherent, but with a sense of fuzziness on the attacks.

Figure 4. Our Breedlove C20 active acoustics augmented guitar, with a hexaphonic pickup and two sound drivers. Two extra drivers are shown here on top of the soundboard for illustration purposes.

7. FUTURE WORK

The augmented guitar presented in this article provides a proof of concept for the implementation of active acoustics with a hexaphonic pickup and a double sound driver system on a folk guitar. The work points towards further research on the issues of the interface and compacting the electronics into the guitar itself. The intention is to develop the guitar within a framework of constant dialogue between artistic praxis (composition and performance) and technological research. The next generation of the active acoustic guitar will be constructed with a luthier in order to optimize the sound driver placement and sonic characteristics. The beginning of a concert praxis with the instrument is planned for autumn 2015.

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